

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B265
Date: 02 Feb 2007
Take Off 07:55:28
Landing: 13:05:56
Flight Time 5h10m28

Campaign: WINTEX - IASI

Operating Area: N Sea

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Foster	Directflight
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Phil Brown	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics	Jim Crawford	FAAM
7	MARSS / FWVS	James Bowles	Met Office
8	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office
9	SWS	Jeff Brown	Met Office
10	AVAPS / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
11	Mission Scientist 2	Richard Cotton	Met Office
12	Observer	Tom Blackmore	Met Office
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Flight Track:

B265 Track 02-FEB-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b265
 Date: 2/2/07
 Project: IASI
 Location: North Sea

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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074425		engine start	-.13 kft	110	
074636		power change	-.13 kft	110	
074747		taxy	-.13 kft	110	start
075528		T/O	-.14 kft	211	from Cranfield
075807		JW / Nevz zero	3.6 kft	030	
075907		Heimann	5.2 kft	034	exposed
080935		bbr	15.0 kft	000	retract
083609		video started	3.9 kft	326	ufc/dfc
084016	090854	Run 1	-.34 - -.31 kft	335	
084446		bbr	-.35 kft	347	retract
084457		low cloud	-.34 kft	344	above
091202	095552	Profile 1	-.35 - 33.0 kft	189	
093234		Profile 1	20.0 kft	177	interrupt
093444		Profile 1	20.0 kft	006	resume
094548		Profile 1	29.0 kft	343	interrupt
094936		Profile 1	29.0 kft	162	resume
095705		bbr	33.0 kft	277	retract
095901	101828	Run 2	33.0 - 33.1 kft	355	
095901		Sonde 1	33.0 kft	346	
100203		Sonde 2	33.0 kft	338	
100504		Sonde 3	33.0 kft	338	
100804		Sonde 4	33.0 kft	339	
101255		Sonde 5	33.0 kft	340	
101543		Sonde 6	33.0 kft	339	
102328	102809	Profile 2	33.1 - 35.0 kft	174	
102529		Sonde 7	33.8 kft	159	
102815	103924	Run 3	35.1 kft	156	
102836		Sonde 8	35.0 kft	157	
103136		Sonde 9	35.0 kft	162	
103437		Sonde 10	35.0 kft	175	
103855		Sonde 11	35.0 kft	177	
104349	110654	Run 4	35.0 kft	351	
104421		Sonde 12	35.0 kft	006	
104717		Sonde 13	35.0 kft	007	
105018		Sonde 14	35.0 kft	340	
105318		Sonde 15	35.0 kft	344	
105819		Sonde 16	35.0 kft	341	
110119		Sonde 17	35.0 kft	340	
110633		Sonde 18	35.1 kft	340	
111142	112345	Run 5	35.1 - 35.0 kft	158	
112624	120131	Profile 3	35.0 - -.37 kft	356	
112635		bbr	35.0 kft	359	extend
115445		Profile 3	1.8 kft	345	interrupt
115635		Profile 3	1.8 kft	161	resume
120223	122331	Run 6	-.33 - -.42 kft	174	
120646		bbr	-.39 kft	174	retract
123612		bbr	15.0 kft	175	extend
130556		Land	-.20 kft	028	Cranfield
131133		standstill	-.20 kft	000	52'04.36N, 0'37.50W

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR ISOBARS AT 4 MB INTERVALS
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION

B265 Track 02-FEB-07

Sortie brief: METOP (IASI) overpass over ocean

Mission Scientist: Phil Brown

Flight B265 02/02/2007

Aim: To measure infrared radiances and the state of the atmosphere for calibration /validation of IASI on METOP-A satellite.

Location: Over open ocean. The mission scientist will determine the area of operations so as to operate in clear skies.

Weather conditions: Completely cloud free conditions at all altitudes are highly desirable; small amounts of cloud in limited areas are acceptable.

Key instruments: ARIES; AVAPS (15 sondes to be launched); temperature and water vapour sensors; Core Chem, MARSS, SAWS hygrometer, FWVS.

Radiation instrument operators' special instructions:

ARIES: At high level mainly nadir, short view of zenith during one run.

At low level one or (preferably) two short views at nadir otherwise mainly zenith.

HEIMANN: Mission scientist should ensure Flight Manager performs short cal of Heimann during the 100ft run(s) (at start or end) but that this does NOT clash with the ARIES nadir views.

Fixed Points: The runs will be over fixed ground positions in clear sky conditions. This sortie is NOT directly under the sub-satellite track so orientation is not critical and should be decided to maximize clear conditions.

A =

B =

1. Take off, transit to operating area arriving at low level (45 mins)
2. Start straight and level run from A to B at lowest permitted altitude (25 mins)
3. Profile ascent from lowest permitted altitude to max altitude at 1000ft/min to finish at point B (45 mins) **Note** that once fuel has been burnt if extra height can be gained then profile up to new max altitude between straight and level runs.
4. Start run from B to A (15 mins)
5. Start run from A to B launching sonde at start of run then every 3 mins (15 mins)
6. Start run from B to A to coincide with **IASI overpass** 1018Z launching sonde at start of run then every 3 mins (15 mins)
7. Start run from A to B launching sonde at start of run then every 3 mins (15 mins)
8. Start run from B to A (15 mins)
9. Start of profile descent from max altitude to lowest permitted altitude @ 1000ft/min to finish at point A (35 mins)
10. Start straight and level run between A and B at lowest permitted altitude (25 mins)
11. Transit home (45 mins)
12. Land (Total sortie time 4:55)

Phil Brown

2 Feb 2007

Planned as a flight to measure up- and down-welling radiances in clear air within the range of the IASI instrument on the METOP satellite.

Transit at 15000ft up the east coast. Came under the edge of upper level cloud at approx 54.2 degN, 0.5 degW as anticipated prior to take-off. Clear conditions ahead and into the experimental area (Firth of Forth region).

Descent to 100ft for near surface run (Run 1). Near the start of this, some minor track adjustments were undertaken to avoid small cloud patches. Apparently clean airmass as judged by PCASP and CN counter outputs. Also low count rate on both SID probes. At N end of run some thin cirrus visible over land just to the east.

Profile ascent on southerly heading to 33000ft. First leg at this altitude was again northbound and sonde dropping was commenced in order that they be concentrated around the satellite overpass time of 1016Z. 6 sondes in total along this leg. In the latter half of the run, some thin cirrus was seen below and clearly identified in Heimann upwelling brightness temperatures.

Profile ascent to 35000ft in order to maximise altitude. Next leg flown on southbound heading. Previous cirrus streak clearly visible below and now to the left (E) of current track. 5 sondes along this leg. Further leg flown at this altitude, northbound and briefly over land during the wide turn at the start. 7 sondes in total along this leg. 18 sondes total for the flight and all apparently OK. Final sonde launched at c. 1106, ie. 50 min after the satellite overpass. One further run at 35000ft, southbound but no further sonde drops.

Profile descent to 100ft on northerly heading, followed by southbound run at 100ft. Climb to return transit altitude.

Overall, the sortie appeared to be very successful with all the required components being achieved. The number of high-level runs was reduced compared to normal sortie of this type, in order to save time just prior to the satellite overpass time. The required clear-sky conditions were generally apparent throughout, with just a thin band of thin cirrus crossing the region during the first high-altitude runs. The period of time for which upwelling radiances will sample this cloud band may be clearly identified from Heimann radiometer data. Post flight note: this cloud band was also clearly visible in visible and IR satellite imagery.

Note also that turns at the end of each high-level run were towards the west (ie. Towards the land). The turn angle was shallow in order to maintain contact with dropsondes, leading to large turn radius that carried the flight track close to land at each end of the run. At the start of the subsequent run, heading was adjusted so as to bring the aircraft back onto the nominal track between fixed points. Some of the data at these times may have sampled sea surface regions closer to the coast that may have temperatures different from those sampled during the 100ft altitude legs.

General synoptic situation.

Anticyclone centred to the SW of Ireland with a warm sector over the UK at midday. Warm front oriented roughly SW to NE crossing the E.coast during the morning to leave clearing skies over near-coastal waters.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.265** Date 2/2/07 Name R. Cooper Page 2 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
064018	R1st	100ft	333	55°24'0 101°2'0	Low level run left of track by 2m to avoid single patch of Ac o/s Ci.
064100		T: 7.8°C	Td: 2.8°C		moving Ac to right of track.
064920		Wind	9 m/s	286°	just avoiding Ac / Sc see flight Ac ahead. just go under slightly.
064900	-085030	T: 7.5°C	Td: 3.5°C	55°54'0 102°4'0	Clear ahead now
					Very clear air now
070851	R2nd	FLB			
071200	P1st	50ft			Clear sky, v. little cloud.
0715		FL035			Poor vis at 2000ft. thin diffuse hazy layers. But o/s Ci above. Some low cloud over coast.
072400		FL114		T: -16°C	Td: -37°C
073220		FL200			Intercept P1 to turn low/mid cloud to left. but drift east
073410	P1 rest	FL200		T: -27°C	Td: -47°C

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.265** Date 2/2/07 Name R. CARTER Page 3 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
094100		FL260	346	55°48.0 1°18.0	wind 48ms / 103k T=-42°C Td=-52°C
					In clear air o/p Ci: Some mid-level in distance * which we passed under in R1.
094245		FL272	turn - 6-7.		
		FL282	still v. turb.		
094640	Pf intercept to		turn. FL 290		Some Sc to east, and some over land.
094940	Pf recovery			still dry.	clear above
095550	Plend	FL330		T=-55 Td=-61	
095900	R2 start	FL330			Sonde Launch run.
				T:-55.6 Td: -64°C	Still in clear air. with lone isolated cloud
				wind 43/900)	Mostly will avoid single high/mid-level cloud
	Thin Ci	over pt. 0, last tenish miles			
					mid level cloud referred to above
101100					just starting to be below aircraft now More high-mid-level cloud at northern end. Point B is under Ci / Cs cloud.
101334	R2 end	FL330		T=-56, Td: -63	Gentle turn.
					Initially missing Ci because starting offset to right
10	R2 start	FL350			Sonde launched during climb to FL350
		Lphg off.		Turb. b.	
101475					In clear air no cloud under / below
					Extending run south past A a
	R2 end				last amount, drop fuel valve.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.261** Date 2/2/07 Name R. COOPER Page 4 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Turbulent.
					Air much clearer to Jubb (A), than north (B), so shift run slightly south.
102920	R3 _{ent}				Assume radio airmail. V. turb. until ~1042 drop sonde during turn hazy.
104352	R4 _{st}	FL350			just before point A. o/p - 1/8 ci around.
105820					clear sky still T _i = -57 T _a = -66°C This last run always in clear air o/p ci.
110654	R4 _{ent}	FL350			drop last sonde during gentle turn at at run out pt B.
111142	R5 _{st}	FL350			T _i = -61°C T _a = -65°C on our track clear o/p ci.
					Very diffuse ci occasionally.
	* Last run	is best	for clear air *		To west, lot of sea cu Some cu over land. to east.
111850	R6 _{st}				
112624	R2 _{st}	FL350		55° 24' 0" 1° 18' 0"	Very hazy. but cloud free To keep within BA will intercept profile, platform turn.
					But running out of time so only incorporate 1 turn to be at pt at 500ft.
115600	FL072	T _i = -76°C		T _a = -22°C	visibility low.
115445	P2				Turn at 2000ft.
115624	P2 recovery.			T _i = 2°C	T _a = -2°C

Mission Scientist's Log

METOP C IASI)

Flight No **B.265** Date 2/2/67 Name R. COTTON Page 1 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Take-off cranfield.
					Very hazy, some mist.
080300		FL122			During climb to transit, in clear air but f/f above 6/8 SC ^(near base) below.
080410		FL135			Into cloud base, turbulence
080650		FL150			out of cloud generally.
					2D sees snow, T _w increases.
0809					In/out of thin AS/Ac
081000					T = -16.1, T _d = -16.9
					Aircraft ^{anti-} icing on
081345		FL150			near base of AS ^{limited} visibility.
081640-50					In/out cloud.
081830		FL150	331	57°54'0 0°18'0	Passing thro fall-strecker turb.
082010					Thru thin cloud layer.
082330		FL150			Exit frontal zone
					Clear above 18' cloud below, but thinning out ahead of us.
0832		FL115		54°54'0 0°54'0	Just clearing SC below.
					Now, ahead is cloud free but hazy.
					some very isolated clouds.
083310		FL088			T _a = 9.3 9.3 T _d = -16
					but isolated mid-level cloud
083600					just in way, to avoid, pass to left.

Mission Scientist's Log #2

Flight No **B**.....265 Date 2/2/07 Name Phil Brown Page 1 of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
0756	en				T/O Coanfield, mist Patched Sc,
0805		15000			Patched As layer. 3 min in cloud, 0.1 gm ³ peak
082330		"	330	54 12.0 0 30.0 W	Just under edge of frontal cloud. Looks clear ahead
084014		100			Start R1 small patch of Sc on R near start
08442					Modifying to avoid small patch of Sc.
084900		"			Just coming under another small clouds
085100					Clear above again.
085420					Shallow Turn back onto track. PCASP / CW concs v. low SID 1 ~ 10/sec SID 2 ~ 1
090525					Meinam cal finish. Tsurf ~ 7.3.
090854					End R1 Ci visible over land
091202		50 2500	189	57.00 -1 42	Start P1 Out of mixed layer.
0917		4500			Frontal cloud visible at low level on S e horizon.

Mission Scientist's Log #2

Flight No **B.265** Date 2/2/07 Name Page 2 of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
0931		19000			Neph picks up aerosol in Blk on, below ~ 1100 m.
0932					Small patches of thin Sc to left of track.
0952		31200	173		Contrail -52.2 / -59.5 Cu on horizon to NE as expected.
0955		33000			End P1
095908					Start R2 / Sonde.
100204					Sonde 2 - disappeared into strat contrail. -55.6 / -62.6
100508					Sonde 3
1005					contrail intermittent.
1006		"	340		Clear above & below.
100803					Sonde 4 sonde 2 GPS appeared.
101255					Sonde 5 sonde 2
101424					Thin Ci below.
101545					Sonde 6 seen on Heiman
101825					End R2
		33000			Start P2 Track displaced due to wide turn.
102536			160		Sonde 7
102810		35000			End P2 / start R3
102837					Sonde 8 contrail intermittent -54.5 / -64.7.
					Clear below.
					Ci streak to left of track & below.

Mission Scientist's Log # 2

Flight No **B.265** Date 2/2/07 Name Page 3 of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
103138		35000	162		Sonde 9
103438					clear below Sonde 10
103857					Sonde 11
103926		35000			End Run south of A. 20000
					Over land briefly during turn.
104349		35000			Start R4 12 mi left of Sonde 12 extended track.
104720			006		Sonde 13.
105020					Sonde 14 went close to port contrail plane.
105320		"	344		Sonde 15
105820					Sonde 16.
110120					Sonde 17 remains clear below - Heiman.
110635					Sonde 18 went into strd contrail. may be persisted trail here.
110654					End R4. -60.6/-66.6
111143		35000			Start R5 11 mi displaced from A/B line.
1123		"			End R5 clear below throughout.
112625		"	0		Start Profile 3
		31000			contrail now start. -52.5/-62
					stop contrail -50.6
		24000			T profile following v closely the original ascent. RH similar.
		15000			RH moister than before.

3h

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B265

Date: 2 feb 07	Operator: jc	DRS Time:	DAU1 Time:	DAU2 Time:	DAU3 Time:	Aux1 Time:	Aux2 Time:	Page 1 of 1
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
080500																Log restarted after word crash! Outbound transit FFSSP logging Sid1 logging Sid2 logging Precip logging	
081000	300	0.12	107	200	10	23	775	?		?						Snow CIP showing no counts 2dp showing some particles but many noise counts, temp -16C	
083000																2dp in clear air producing bursts of 1 bit noise.	
084016	32	0.1	143	10	1	0	0	0	0	?						Clear air run 1	
085000	19	0.14	143	20	1	0	0	0	0								
090000	20	0.12	144	20	2	0	0	0	0								
090500	35	0.11	145	20	2	0	0	0	0								
090854	55	0.10	145	20	2	0	0	0	0							End run 1	
091202	63	0.01	146	20	2	0	0	0	0							Start profile 1	
091500	25	0.11	146	20	2	0	0	0	0							2000ft	
091700	8	0.11	146	0	0	0	0	0	0							FI045	
091830	8	0.10	146	0	0	0	0	0	0							FI060	
092015	3	0.07	146	0	0	0	0	0	0							FI075	
092140	4	0.12	146	0	0	0	0	0	0							FI090	
092315	8	0.11	146	0	0	0	0	0	0							FI105	
092440	7	0.11	146	0	0	0	0	0	0							FI120	
092610	20	0.08	146	0	0	0	0	0	0							FI135	
092740	8	0.11	146	0	0	0	0	0	0							FI150	
092900	6	0.12	146	0	0	0	0	0	0							FI165	
093120																PCASP off - noise from sws motor	
093240	off	off	146	0	0	0	0	0	0							FI200	
Cloud physics console unattended during sonde dropping																	
111640	on	on														PCASP on - sws motor off 2dc intermittent 1 bit noise	
112320								off	off							2dp noise - alignment - switched off @-56C	
113000	Inboard screen collapsed on power switches despite blocking box. SID1 computer restarted with scan disk - saved files in file0001.chk - may be recoverable																
	Power to precip lost - computer not restarted in order to protect data files. Will attempt recovery with appropriate tools																
114400	Sid1 restarted as b265b																

FAAM Dropsonde Flight Log

Flight No.	B265	Date	02 Feb 2007
Page No.	1 of 1	Operator	Doug Anderson

GMT	Sonde No.	Event	Comments
095903	1	Launch	261.70 -55.40 33.87 304.30 45.80 - 19.20 -1.339800 55.455600 10065.70
101110	1	Splash Down	1030.83 7.93 72.05 304.80 9.78 - 9.84 -1.147892 55.312353
100203	2	Launch	261.90 -55.80 43.37 308.20 48.50 - 16.10 -1.310000 55.708100 0059.60
101349	2	Splash Down	9999.00 99.00 999.00 293.15 11.01 - 11.67 -1.120250 55.566497 99999.00
100506	3	Launch	261.40 -55.50 40.20 307.80 45.90 - 18.50 -1.393600 55.943100 10071.80
101646	3	Splash Down	9999.00 99.00 999.00 292.04 10.42 - 10.92 -1.192575 55.799446 99999.00
100805	4	Launch	261.90 -55.30 39.75 310.40 50.20 - 15.70 -1.469217 56.171253 10042.88
102005	4	Splash Down	9999.00 99.00 999.00 296.02 11.37 - 11.37 -1.261716 56.025077 99999.00
101257	5	Launch	261.60 -55.80 41.69 312.60 48.80 - 16.90 -1.600200 56.562700 10068.10
102431	5	Splash Down	9999.00 99.00 999.00 277.49 10.81 - 11.34 -1.394603 56.405628 99999.00
101545	6	Launch	261.40 -55.50 44.64 312.10 51.60 - 15.20 -1.676200 56.785400 10074.20
102729	6	Splash Down	9999.00 99.00 999.00 341.52 2.03 - 1.25 -1.462257 56.626259 99999.00
102530	7	Launch	251.90 -58.10 55.41 299.20 43.30 - 17.40 -2.023100 56.618000 10312.30
103715	7	Splash Down	9999.00 99.00 999.00 274.49 9.98 - 10.33 -1.813875 56.453934 99999.00
102836	8	Launch	238.60 -55.70 32.86 303.90 37.40 - 20.00 -1.705700 56.299800 10662.10
104045	8	Splash Down	9999.00 99.00 999.00 292.86 11.72 - 11.47 -1.490427 56.133716 99999.00
103139	9	Launch	238.20 -55.30 29.66 302.00 29.10 - 17.40 -1.430600 55.987900 10673.80
104323	9	Splash Down	1030.76 7.34 75.92 286.17 12.84 - 11.21 -1.223526 55.838351 86.50
103439	10	Launch	238.20 -55.70 29.90 294.90 29.30 - 17.50 -1.302900 55.659900 10674.40
104656	10	Splash Down	9999.00 99.00 999.00 33.53 0.55 0.00 -1.104053 55.518034 99999.00
103857	11	Launch	238.70 -56.30 29.27 283.70 28.60 - 17.80 -1.144300 55.182000 10660.10
105112	11	Splash Down	9999.00 99.00 999.00 290.54 8.13 - 8.35 -0.956099 55.050389 99999.00
104421	12	Launch	238.10 -56.30 26.96 307.90 31.10 - 16.90 -1.491000 55.094700 10676.90
105632	12	Splash Down	9999.00 99.00 999.00 293.74 8.39 - 10.86 -1.315765 54.959249 99999.00
104721	13	Launch	238.10 -56.20 29.71 311.30 37.60 - 17.00 -1.335800 55.366200 10675.40
105928	13	Splash Down	9999.00 99.00 999.00 305.12 11.31 - 11.24 -1.145804 55.22513 99999.00
105021	14	Launch	237.90 -57.70 34.80 314.50 44.30 - 15.70 -1.298300 55.633700 10680.90
110220	14	Splash Down	1030.88 7.56 70.14 296.79 12.22 - 11.15 -1.104512 55.481936 65.63
105318	15	Launch	238.10 -55.20 24.90 315.40 36.90 - 14.30 -1.376800 55.891100 10676.60
110519	15	Splash Down	1029.95 7.56 71.58 296.25 13.58 - 10.84 -1.175575 55.734595 69.95

105827	16	Launch	238.30	-57.00	31.90	318.40	52.20	-
			14.80	-1.523500	56.335900		10670.80	
111033	16	Splash Down	1030.92	7.28	70.35	288.71	11.30	-
			10.40	-1.304777	56.156349		99.80	
110121	17	Launch	238.10	-60.10	46.48	313.50	60.70	-
			15.40	-1.606100	56.580600		10676.30	
111337	17	Splash Down	1029.89	7.46	66.60	285.14	11.78	-
			10.98	-1.381228	56.403541		99999.00	
110636	18	Launch	237.90	-61.10	48.03	309.50	58.10	-
			15.10	-1.734500	57.012600		10680.80	
111859	18	Splash Down	1030.03	7.55	66.41	296.97	10.50	-
			10.90	-1.502589	56.831640		125.07	

SWS and SHIMS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight # **B265** Date **2/2/07** Operat or(s) **JEFF BROWN** log page **1** of **3**

Note to operator: Indicate whether entry refers to SWS or SHIMS

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	S W S	U S H	L S H
				Vis	NIR				
0626		-				All modules working OK. "Video" circuit breaker now working.			
0739				1000			✓		
				1000				✓	
				1000					✓
0758			174° A			Head to Nadir for transit 718 St/Sc 518 Ac/As 1/8 Li			
0804		14000	174° A			Into Ac/As layer at FL140			
0816		15000	174° A			Ac/As			
082724		15000	174° A	750		Dark		✓	
082740		15000	174° A	750		Scene		✓	
083735		1200	6° F			SWS Head To Zenith			
084016	R1	100	6° F			Start of run			
084907	R1	100	6° F			Under small patch low cloud			
085100	R1	100	6° F			Cloud free again			
090854	R1	100	6° F			End of run.			
091948	P1	8000	6° F	750		Scene Dark			✓
092018	P1	8000	6° F	750		Scene			✓
092450	P1	13000	6° F	1000		DARK			✓
092525	P1	13000	6° F	1000		Scene			✓
092816	P1	16500	6° F	500		DARK		✓	
092847	P1	16500	6° F	500		Scene		✓	
093050	P1	18800	6° F			MOTOR ON - PCASP DIGS!			
093558	P1	21400	6° F	400		DARK			
				400					
093731	P1		6° F			DARK All - NO FOOT LINES RESET SHUTTERS + DARK All AGAIN - SORTED!			
093828	P1	23900	6° F	1000		SCENE ALL	✓		
			6° F	400					✓
			6° F	1000					✓
094015	P1	26000	6° F	750		DARK			✓
094029	P1	26000	6° F	750		Scene			✓
09443	P1		174° A			Head to Nadir ready for run			
094447	P1	28700		1000		DARK			✓
094546	P1	18700		1000		Scene			✓
095844	R2	33000	174° A	350		Dark all		✓	
095925	R2	33000	174° A	750		Scene all			✓
						SWS Head Frozen at 20° F			
100400	R2	33000	174° A			Managed to get back to Nadir			
1010	R2	33000	174° A			In above thin Ci			✓
101124	R2	33000	174° A	500		DARK All		✓	
101153	R2	33000	174° A	500		Scene All			✓
1014						Motor off as SWS head (rotating) slightly (with vibration of Alt)			
						Motor Back on			
1023									
103550	R2	36000	174° A	750		DARK		✓	
103605	R2	35000	174° A	750		Scene		✓	
1040		35000	6° F			SWS Head to Zenith			
104350	R3	35000	6° F						

* SWS head 'refused' to sit at 177 AFT + kept reverting back to 174° AFT. Same happened when set to 171 AFT. POSSIBLY SLIP STREAM HITTING MOUNT WINDOW.

SWS and SHIMS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight # **B 265** Date **2/2/07** Operat or(s) **JOFF BROWN** log page **2** of **3**

Note to operator: Indicate whether entry refers to SWS or SHIMS

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	S W S	U S H	L S H
				Vis	NIR				
104450	R2	35000	6° F	1000		Dark All	✓		
104515	R2	35000	6° F	300		Scene All		✓	
104700	R2	35000	174° F			SWS HEAD TO ZENITH			
104744	R2	35000	174° F	750		DARK	✓		
104806	R2	35000	174° F	750		Scene	✓		
112713	P3	34500	174° F	250		Dark all	✓	✓	
112740	P3	34500	174° F	1000		Scene all		✓	✓
	P3					Angle box required			
	P3					re-aligning.			
114650	P3	9500	174° F	1000	1000	Dark	✓		
114721	P3	9500	174° F	1000	1000	Scene	✓		
120508	R3	100	6° A			SWS head to Zenith			
120536	R3	100	6° A	750		Dark	✓		
120556	R3	100	6° A	750		Scene	✓		
120649	R3	100	6° A			Sudden rise on LSH			✓
						Perd ice falling off?			✓
120937	R3	100	6° A	300		Dark		✓	
121003	R3	100	6° A	300		Scene		✓	
122000	R3	100	174° F	1000		Scene	✓		
	R3	100	174° F	1000		Dark	✓		

ARIES flight log

Flight: B265

page 1 of 4

Date: 02/FEB/167 Operator(s): S. Rogers

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: NORTH SEA / CLEAR SKIES / METOP

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
06:32:30	Ground	1x60	C	C	71	31	
06:33	"	"	H	C	71	31	
07:55	TAKE OFF						
08:11:00	^{Transit} FL 150?	1x60	C	C	71	31	Transit - mostly in cloud.
08:11:34		"	H	C	71	31	
08:39:58	R1	1x60	C	C			
08:40:33		"	H	C	71	31	
08:41		240x1	N	C	71	30	
08:43:22		1x60	C	C	71	31	
08:44:06		"	H	C			
08:44:47		240x1	Z	O	70	31	Clear above
08:47:50		1x60	C	C			
08:48:25		"	H	C	71	31	
08:49:10		240x1	Z	O	70	30	Some Cu above clear at end?
08:52:10		1x60	C	C	71	31	This horizon ^{at} horizon
08:52:51		"	H	C	71	31	
08:53:30		240x1	Z	O	70	31	Clear above. Some v. small Cu.
08:56:20		1x60	C	C	71	31	
08:56:54		"	H	C	71	31	
08:57:32		240x1	Z	O	70	31	Open shutter late. Clear above.
09:00:30		1x60	C	C	71	31	
09:01:08		"	H	C	71	31	
09:01:50		180x1	Z	O	70	31	Clear above
09:04:30		1x60	C	C	71	31	
09:05:04		"	H	C	71	31	
09:06:19		120x1	Z	O	70	31	Clear above
09:08:25		1x60	C	C	71	31	
09:09:01		"	H	C	70	31	End of run at start of H view
09:12	P1 ↑						From several thousand feet up, the preceding run looks to be in some haze.

ARIES flight log

Flight: B265

page 2 of 4

Date:

Operator(s):

Res:

Gain A: B:

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
09 59 06	R2	1 x 60	C	C	71	30	
09 59 36		"	H	C			SWS unable to look up - too cold.
10 00 20		180 x 1	Z	B	70	30	Clear above (v.v. thin G ???)
10 02 50		1 x 60	C	C	71	31	
10 03 24		"	H	C	70.5	30.5	
10 04 05		240 x 1	N	C	70.5	30	Haze below, white horses visible on sea.
10 06 16		1 x 60	C	C	70	31	
10 06 51		"	H	C	70	31	
10 07 37		240 x 1	N	C			Some thin cloud below near end of view
10 09 46		1 x 60	C	C	70	31	
10 10 20		"	H	C			
10 10 54		240 x 1	N	C	71	30	Thickening cloud below
10 13 07		1 x 60	C	C	70	30	
10 13 40		"	H	C	71	31	
10 14 32		240 x 1	N	C	71	30	Cloud below. fairly uniform
10 16 39		1 x 60	C	C	70	30	
10 17 21		"	H	C			
10 23	P2 ↑						
10 28 16	R High	1 x 60	C	C	71	31	Some confusion here - didn't stop when expected
10 30 10		1 x 60	B C	C			
10 30 46		"	H	C			
10 31 25		120 x 1	Z	O	70	31	V. thin G above??
10 33 20		1 x 60	C	C			
10 33 54		"	H	C			
10 34 31		240 x 1	N	C	71	31	Fairly clear below, some haze
10 36 09		1 x 60	C	C	71	31	
10 36 42		"	H	C	70	30	
10 43 31	R Higher	1 x 60	C	C			
10 44 02		"	H	C			
10 44 40		60 x 1	Z	O	70	30	
10 45 45		1 x 60	C	C			
10 46 20			H	C	71	30	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B265

page 3 of 4

Date:

Operator(s):

Res:

Gain A: B:

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
10 47 00		240x1	N	C	71	31	fairly clear below, white horses visible
10 49 07		1x60	C	C	71	30	
10 49 43		"	H	C	71	31	
10 50 19		240x1	N	C	71	31	— —
10 52 30		1x60	C	C	71	30	Turbulent.
10 53 03		"	H	C			
10 53 46		180x1	N	C			fairly clear, some haze
10 55 25		1x60	C	C	71	30	
10 55 57		"	H	C			
10 56 35		240x1	N	C	71	30	Still bumpy. A little hazier.
10 58 42		1x60	C	C	71	30	
10 59 17		"	H	C	71	30	
10 59 59		180x1	N	C	71	31	Hazy below, sea still visible.
11 01 36		1x60	C	C	71	30	
11 02 09			H	C			
11 02 55		180x1	N	C	71	31	
11 04 33		1x60	C	C	71	30	
11 05 11		"	H	C			
11 11 43	R	1x60	C	C			
11 12 18		"	H	C	71	30	
11 13		300x1	N	C	71	31	
11 15 42		1x60	C	C	71	31	
11 16 15		"	H	C			
11 16 54		300x1	N	C	71	30	Hazy below. Sea visible.
11 19 30		1x60	C	C	70	31	
11 20 03		"	H	C			
11 20 42		240x1	N	C	71	31	A bit bumpier
11 22 49		1x60	C	C			
11 23 24		"	H	C	71	31	
11:26	P ↓						

ARIES flight log

Flight: 13265

page 4 of 4

Date: Operator(s): Res: Gain A: B:

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
12 01 02	10off	1x60	C	C			
12 01 38		"	H	C	71	30	
12 02 15		120x1	N	C	71	31	Some white haze. Not too dense
12 03 25		1x60	C	C			Slightly blurry side Alan wouldn't like it.
12 03 59		"	H	C			
12 04 39		240x1	Z	O	70	30	Clear above. slight haze on horizon.
12 07 35		1x60	C	C	71	31	
12 08 08		"	H	C			
12 08 46		180x1	Z	O	71	31	Clear above
12 11 10		1x60	C	C	71	30	
12 11 43		"	H	C			
12 26		180x1?	Z	O			
12 14 13		1x60	C	C	71		cal unit Heiman dead? Retrying.
12 14 55		"	H	C			
12 15 52		180x1	Z	O			16:25 shots. Clear above Haze on horizon
12 18 20		1x60	C	C			
12 18 53		"	H	C	71	31	Heiman cal unit partially working
12 19 45		120x1	N	C	71	31	
12 20 52		1x60	C	C	71	31	
12 21 28		"	H	C	71	31	
							Climbing. As before, haze at low level is obvious from above.

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG	Date	2/1/07	Flight	B265	log pages
Operator(s)	JB	Campaign	IASI Cal Val		
Departure	Cranfield	Arrival	Cranfield		

**System start
MARSS**

Visual pod inspection					•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers					•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers					•
FERA on			at time	0629	
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	16.8	Ch	16.7	Ch18 16.3
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20 40°C
MARSS CPU on			at time	06:30	
Initial target temperatures	Hot	288.8	Cold	284.0	
Target heating					•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***					•
Scanning on (LMD box)			at time	0633	
Scan indication		Monitor	•	Visual	•

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers	Not Switched on				
Turn on Deimos CPU					
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***					
Start Deimos Software			at time		
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold		
Target heating					
Scan indication		Monitor		Visual	
Weather	Cloud	Low cloud 8/8	Precip	drissel	
	Surface	Dry	Pressure		
	Other				

System functionality check (after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	0638	
Brightness temps 'sensible'				•	
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot 344.5	Cold 284.8		
	Deimos:	Hot	Cold		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A (-)	Ch3 A (-)	Ch1 B (-)	Ch3 B (-)	
	Ch16 (40-44)	Ch17 (45-49)	Ch18 (40-44)	Ch19 (40-44)	Ch20 (44-48)
	42.88	33.0	38.5	40.72	42.9

Power changeover

Headset on before start		•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.	•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)		•
Exit Deimos Software (x)		
POWER CHANGEOVER		
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton	•
Restart Deimos Software		
System running again		at time

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG	Date	2/1/07	Flight	B265	log pages
Operator(s)	JB	Campaign	IASI Cal Val		
Departure	Cranfield	Arrival	Cranfield		

**System start
MARSS**

Visual pod inspection					•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers					•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers					•
FERA on			at time	0629	
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	16.8	Ch	16.7	Ch18 16.3
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20 40°C
MARSS CPU on			at time	06:30	
Initial target temperatures	Hot	288.8	Cold	284.0	
Target heating					•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***					•
Scanning on (LMD box)			at time	0633	
Scan indication		Monitor	•	Visual	•

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers	Not Switched on				
Turn on Deimos CPU					
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***					
Start Deimos Software			at time		
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold		
Target heating					
Scan indication		Monitor		Visual	
Weather	Cloud	Low cloud 8/8	Precip	drissel	
	Surface	Dry	Pressure		
	Other				

System functionality check (after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	0638
Brightness temps 'sensible'				•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot 344.5	Cold 284.8	
	Deimos:	Hot	Cold	
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)
	42.88	33.0	38.5	40.72
				Ch20
				(44-48)
				42.9

Power changeover

Headset on before start		•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.	•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)		•
Exit Deimos Software (x)		
POWER CHANGEOVER		
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton	•
Restart Deimos Software		
System running again		at time

Flight:

B265

KEY

Duff Data	
Minor Problems	
	OK

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevezorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turbulence Check Press:
- Turbulence Diff Press:
- Weather Radar:

DLUs:

- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:

Aerosol

- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3010A:
- INC:
- VACC:

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Report Created 05/02/2007 11:37:41

Last Updated:

05/02/2007 10:02:48

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B265

Date: 02 February 2007

Instruments

1. Nevzorov Liquid water circuit u/s
2. Nephelometer sp data being baseline-clipped
3. Mission Scientist laptop p/s cable problem
4. Heimann Calibration on the blink. First cal good but second cal needed a bit of persuading after high level operation. Had to try three times and resulting cal was around 2 degs lower than previous.

Aircraft

Satcom H Calls

None

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 2/2/07

Flight No: B265

Pre-Flighter: PAPT

<u>Item</u>	<u>✓ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
<u>Aircraft Cabin</u>				
2	<input type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	no CO
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	-?
12	<input type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	no.
13	<input type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	no
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	no CO
16	<input type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	no
17	<input type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up	no not filled
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	not filled
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	no
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	<input type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	no
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			

External Checks overleaf →

Pre-Flighter's Log

<u>Item</u> ✓ or x	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<u>External</u>			
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TWC Cover	Fitted if required	<i>not fitted</i>
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All other covers	Removed	
40	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>			Signed
43	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
44	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ICEX applied		
45	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Traps empty (weekly only)		

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B265:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics Processing	Awaiting processing completion
Core Chemistry	pre flight only, unmanned operation on auto calibrate so no In Flight log

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	26 Mar 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Upward Facing Cameras
3 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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